

Studies on N-Arylhydroxamic Acid. Part V. N-*m*-Tolyl-*m*-Nitrobenzohydroxamic Acid : Spectrophotometric Reagent for Vanadium(V)

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A reagent N-*m*-tolyl-*m*-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid for the extraction and spectrophotometric determination of vanadium(V) is described. The vanadium(V)-N-*m*-tolyl-*m*-nitrobenzohydroxamate complex is extracted with chloroform from 6-8 *M* hydrochloric acid. It forms the violet complex which obeys Beer's Law at the maximum absorbance of 540 nm with the molar absorptivity $3.1 \times 10^4 \text{ M litre mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The interference of titanium(IV) has been eliminated. The effects of acidity, reagent concentration and diverse ions on the extraction are discussed.

THE N-*m*-Tolyl-*m*-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid (N-*m*-TNBHA) is used successfully as a reagent for the gravimetric determination of several cations¹⁻⁴. The N-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid⁵⁻⁷ and other substituted hydroxamic acids⁸⁻¹¹ extensively used for the spectrophotometric determination of uranium, vanadium etc. Generally, titanium(IV) interfere in the extraction and spectrometric determination of vanadium(V). With this view in the present communication a method has been developed for the rapid extraction and simultaneous spectrophotometric determination of vanadium in presence of titanium.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of AnalaR or G.R. grades of B.D.H. or E. Merck unless otherwise specified.

Reagents: N-*m*-Tolyl-*m*-nitrobenzohydroxamic acid was prepared by the method described elsewhere^{1,2}. Its purity was checked by m.p., elemental analysis, UV and IR spectra and T.L.C.

A 0.1%W/V reagent solution was prepared by dissolving requisite amount of N-*m*-TNBHA in ethanol free chloroform.

A standard vanadium stock solution was prepared by dissolving 0.6260 g. ammonium meta vanadate in a litre of double distilled water. Its vanadium content was determined volumetrically¹³.

Apparatus: The absorption spectra were recorded with a Hilger and Watts, Ultrascan spectrophotometer and the absorbance at a particular wavelength was measured with a Beckman DU-2 spectrophotometer using 10 mm quartz cell.

Procedure for Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Vanadium(V)

5 ml of vanadium(V) ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$) solution was transferred into a 100 ml separatory funnel along with 5 ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid and diluted with distilled water to keep the final molarity of hydrochloric acid at 6-8 *M*. Then 5 ml of chloroform solution of N-*m*-TNBHA was added. The contents were shaken for 5-10 min and chloroform layer was allowed to separate. The violet extract thus obtained was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate to remove the moisture and transferred into 25 ml volumetric flask. To ensure the complete recovery of vanadium the aqueous layer was extracted thrice with 3 ml of reagent solution and sodium sulphate was washed with 2 ml(x3) of chloroform to remove the last traces of violet colour. Finally, the extracts were diluted to 25 ml. The spectra was recorded and the absorbance of violet complex was measured at 540 nm against reagent blank. The results obtained were found to be accurate $\pm 0.5\%$.

Results and Discussion

The spectral characteristic of the complex is given in Table I.

TABLE-1 SPECTRAL CHARACTERISTICS OF VANADIUM-N-*m*-TOLYL-*m*-NITROBENZOHYDROXAMIC ACID COLOURED SYSTEM IN CHLOROFORM

Concentration of acid (<i>M</i>)	Colour of Chloroform extract	Wavelength of maximum absorption	Molar absorptivity (ϵ)
0.01	Amethyst	475	2100
0.10	Pinkish Violet	490	—
1.00	Reddish Violet	505	—
3.00	Reddish Violet	510	2500
4.00	Reddish Violet	510	2600
6.00	Violet	540	3100
7.00	Violet	540	3100
8.00	Violet	540	3100

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Absorption Spectra

The absorption spectrum of violet extract of complex of vanadium(V)-N-*m*-TNBHA is shown in Fig. 1. The maximum absorbance is at 540 nm. It is reproducible and all the measurements were made at this wavelength. The reagent does not show any absorbance maxima between 350 and 540 nm.

Fig. 1

ABSORPTION SPECTRA OF VANADIUM (V)-
N - m TOLYL - m NITROBENZOHYDROXAMIC
ACID COMPLEXES

Fig. 2

EFFECT OF ACIDITY IN EXTRACTION
OF VANADIUM (V)

TABLE—2 EXTRACTION OF VANADIUM(V)-N-*m*-TOLYL-*m*.
NITROBENZOHYDROXAMIC ACID COMPLEX AS A
FUNCTION OF pH

pH	Extraction (%E)	Distribution Ratio (D)
Ca. 0.1	100	a
Ca. 0.2	100	a
Ca. 0.3	100	a
0.5	100	a
1.0	100	a
1.5	96	86
2.0	70	40
2.5	45	11
3.0	20	0.8

a= Too high to measure.

Beer's Law

The chloroform violet extract obeys Beer's Law over the range of 1 to 15 ppm of vanadium at 540 nm. The molar absorptivity at 540 nm is found to be 3.1×10^4 mol lit⁻¹.

Effect of pH

The maximum colour intensity was obtained with 6-8M HCl. The effect of acidity on the extraction system is shown in fig. 2 and distribution data at different pH are given in Table 2. It can be seen that the extraction is complete at pH 1 or <1 and the distribution ratio has infinite value at this pH.

Effect of Reagent Concentration and Time

The reagent have no effect on the colour system and hence a large excess of reagent can be used for extraction purposes. However, a 10 ml of 0.1% (W/V) of reagent was sufficient for recovery of vanadium(V). The colour is stable for several days.

Extraction of vanadium complex is very rapid. Shaking for 30 sec. was enough to attain the equilibrium when the reagent was added to the aqueous phase and 50-60 sec. was satisfactory for the complete recovery of vanadium.

Effect of Diverse Ions

In order to examine the utility of this method in presence of other ions, their interferences were studied. Ten ppm of vanadium(V) was determined in the presence of the following ions Ag⁺(100), Be²⁺(100), Mg²⁺(100), Ca²⁺(100), Sr²⁺(100), Ba²⁺(100), Cu²⁺(80), Cd²⁺(80), Zn²⁺(80), Hg²⁺(100), Pb²⁺(100), Mn²⁺(80), Co²⁺(80), Ni²⁺(80), UO₂²⁺(70), Ga³⁺(100), La³⁺(100), As³⁺(100), Fe³⁺(70), Cr³⁺(70), Sb³⁺(80), In³⁺(80), Th⁴⁺(80) and WO₂²⁺(70). But generally titanium, large amount of molybdenum and zirconium interfere. These interferences were eliminated by adding a oxalate and citrate(0.1M) prior to extraction of vanadium(V). Ti(IV), Zr(IV) and Mo(VI) forms the strong complexes with oxalate and citrate while vanadium(V) does not give any complex and they can be extracted as before.

Volume of Aqueous Phase and Ionic Strength

The volume of aqueous phase can vary between 25 and 100 ml without affecting the complex formation and extraction. Also upto 10 gm of NaCl per 50 ml volume could be present in the extracted solution without adversely affecting the extraction of vanadium N-*m*-TNBHA complex.

Structure of the V-N-*m*-TNBHA Complex

A study was made to determine the composition of V-N-*m*-TNBHA by the method of continuous variations. The graphical plot of absorbance versus mole fraction of vanadium to vanadium-plus-N-*m*-TNBHA shows well defined maximum at a mole fraction of 0.33 vanadium indicating that one atom of vanadium combines with two moles of N-*m*-tolyl-*m*-nitrobenzo-hydroxamic acid.

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